

Coach Behavior and Student-Athlete Self-Perception

Thesis Manuscript

Submitted to Southern Utah University

College of Humanities and Social Sciences

Department of Communication

in Partial Fulfillment of the

Requirements for the Degree of

MASTER OF ARTS IN PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATION

by

CIERA MARTIN

Cedar City, Utah

April 2023

Abstract

This study aims to research the perceptions of collegiate coaches' behavior and how this can affect student-athlete's perceptions of their performance, communication and interpersonal relationship with their coaches and teammates. Previous research primarily relied on the psychological aspect of motivation and determination for a student-athlete to better enhance their performance, but was unable to understand the fear and perception a coach can affect a student-athlete's overall mental, emotional and physical state. Self-Determination Theory (SDT) is used to determine methodology, questions of the interview for the research. Student-athletes from the basketball and gymnastics team at Southern Utah University were interviewed for this research. This study utilized semi-structured interviews to gather data from student-athletes from different sport teams at Southern Utah University. The study explored various aspects of coaches' behavior, ability to build relationships and their communication style with student-athletes. The findings of this study provide insights to student-athletes' perception of their coach's behavior and how it affects the student-athletes performance during practice or competition. Findings also contribute to student-athletes' mental and emotional wellness, providing coaches with resources and knowledge of effective team communication. This study emphasizes the importance of student-athlete relationships, communication, and perception of their coach's behavior.

Acknowledgments

Words can't express my gratitude to my professor and chair of my graduate capstone committee, Dr. Hayden Coombs, for his invaluable feedback and patience throughout this semester. His sacrifice and support made this research possible. He encouraged me to be a better student, but also a wife, friend, mother, and person. I am very grateful to him and his family.

I am also very grateful to my husband and my daughter who both have sacrificed a lot of time over the past two years. They have been my motivation to do my research and finish my master's degree. All the late nights, weekends, and missing sporting events to complete my assignments couldn't have been done without their support and love.

Lastly, I want to thank all my professors in the SUU Communication department and everyone I have worked with or met during my time at Southern Utah University. All of their support and encouraging words were very much appreciated. I will always be grateful to them to continue to encourage me to pursue my goals. I will miss my time as a T-bird, but I look forward to the many adventures ahead.

Table of Contents

Chapter 1: Introduction	5
Justification.....	5
Introduction to Theoretical Framework.....	6
Introduction to Research Method.....	7
Research Questions.....	8
Summary.....	8
 Chapter 2: Literature Review	 10
Theoretical Framework: Self-Determination Theory.....	10
Self-Determination Theory & Athletics.....	11
Coach-Athlete Relational Dyad.....	12
Summary.....	15
 Chapter 3: Research Method	 16
Research Methodology and Design.....	16
Population and Sample.....	17
Materials.....	18
Study Procedures.....	19
Data Analysis.....	19
Assumptions.....	20
Limitations.....	21
Delimitations.....	21
Ethical Assurances.....	22
Summary.....	22
 Chapter 4: Findings	 24
Trustworthiness of the Data.....	24
Results.....	25
Evaluation of the Findings.....	28
Summary.....	29
 Chapter 5: Implications, Recommendations, and Conclusions	 31
Implications.....	32
Recommendations for Practice.....	33
Recommendations for Future Research.....	34
Conclusions.....	35
 References	 37
 Appendices	 42
Appendix A: Consent Letter.....	42
Appendix B: Interview Guide.....	46
Appendix C: IRB Approval Letter.....	47
Appendix D: SUU Institutional Repository Permission Form.....	48

Chapter 1: Introduction

This study investigates collegiate athletic coaches' behaviors and how this behavior may affect student-athletes' perceptions of their performance or relationship with their coaching staffs and teammates. Over the past few decades, coaches have changed their style and approach to better-suit their athletes' performance (Horn, 2008). The tenets of this study assumes that a coach's behavior, communication, and relationships with their athletes affects the athletes' performance and their ability to be successful in their sport. A thematic analysis analyzed through the lens of Self-Determination Theory (SDT) was utilized in this study. Current senior collegiate athletes who have spent three or more years on each of their respective athletic teams served as the research subjects. The participants were recruited through the Southern Utah University Department of Athletics. Subjects took part in semi-structured interviews to discuss their coach-athlete relationships, personal performance, and communication channels with their coaches. The research questions and interview protocol followed seminal literature on SDT, which suggests that both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation are highly influential determinants of our behavior, and both drive us to meet the three basic needs identified by the SDT model, autonomy, competence, and relatedness. This study emphasizes the importance of one's behavior and how athlete's perceive their coach's behavior, communication, and relationships they are creating.

Justification

The relationship between a collegiate athlete and coach builds over a time span of recruiting, training, traveling, and studying the sport. The amount of hours a collegiate coach and athlete spend together through their college experience is equivalent to a full-time job (Hollembek & Amorose, 2007). With the many hours an athlete spends with their coaching

staff, a relationship is going to be built. With training, instruction, feedback, behavior and social support maintaining the relationship between a coach and athlete is important (Hollebeak & Amorose, 2007). The importance of maintaining a strong relationship with communication between the coach and the athlete can influence the athlete's performance (Horn, 2008). According to Horn (2008), the different behaviors of a coach can influence the athlete to perform differently. Based on the positive or negative portraying from the coaching staff can alter the athlete's success in practice or competition. Success and winning is both important to the coaching staff and athlete, but the overall well-being of the athlete is as important.

In addition to the emotional and relational needs of student-athletes, coaches and athletic administrators also must provide healthy environments for their student-athletes because of the substantial amount of money spent in collegiate athletics. During the 2019-2020 academic school year, institutions of higher education awarded approximately \$4.23 billion of athletic scholarships to cover tuition and fees, room, board, and course-related books, with \$2.76 billion going to student-athletes in NCAA Division I (Knoester & Ridpath, 2021; NCAA, n.d.; Scholarship Stats, 2021). This number does not include the costs required to recruit a student-athlete, which is also a substantial financial investment.

Introduction to Theoretical Framework

Self-Determination Theory (SDT) represents a broad framework for the study of human motivation and personality (Deci & Ryan, 2012). SDT is often used to frame motivational studies in order to define intrinsic and varied extrinsic sources of motivation, and to provide social scientists with a description of the respective roles of intrinsic and types of extrinsic motivation in cognitive and social development and in individual differences (Deci & Ryan, 2012). SDT focuses on how social and cultural factors facilitate or undermine one's sense of

volition and initiative, in addition to their well-being and the quality of their performance (Bentzen et al., 2014).

SDT posits that there are two main types of motivation, intrinsic and extrinsic, and that both are powerful forces in shaping who we are and how we behave (Ryan & Deci, 2000). According to Deci and Ryan, extrinsic motivation is a drive to behave in certain ways based on external sources and it results in external rewards (1985). Such sources include grading systems, employee evaluations, awards and accolades, and the respect and admiration of others. Conversely, intrinsic motivation comes from within. There are internal drives that inspire us to behave in certain ways, including our core values, our interests, and our personal sense of morality (Deci & Ryan, 1985).

SDT has been used in numerous studies exploring sports and athletics, as it offers a sound theoretical framework to better understand the motivational processes leading to serious positive and negative outcomes (Standage & Ryan, 2020). Bartholomew et al. raised awareness on the negative side of sport participation in their 2009 study, which proposed that coach behaviors employed to pressure or control athletes have the potential to thwart athletes' feelings of autonomy, competence, and relatedness, which, in turn, undermine athletes' self-determined motivation and contribute to the development of controlled motives. In 2014, Bentzen et al. conducted a study on four professional athletic coaches who had reported a wide range of burnout symptoms. Findings indicated that athletic coaches experience working in maladaptive environments, exemplified by experiencing very heavy workloads, a lack of leader support, and work-related conflicts (Bentzen et al., 2014). A 2006 study by Amorose and Anderson-Butcher further strengthened the applicability of SDT in sport and athletic participation.

Introduction to Research Method

A thematic analysis research design through the lens of Self-Determination Theory (SDT) was utilized for this study. The three basic needs of SDT, competence, autonomy, and

relatedness provided the themes and guiding framework employed throughout this study. Braun and Clark (2019) explained that thematic analyses are appropriate to use when seeking to understand lived experiences. If the objective of a qualitative study is to construct a comprehensive portrait of a phenomena, researchers can study several instances of the phenomena to identify commonalities (Ragin & Amoroso, 2019). According to Yin (2018), there are six steps to a thematic analysis: planning, designing, preparing, collecting, analyzing, and sharing.

Research Questions

The study focuses on how a coach's behavior affects the athlete's relationship with one another, communication, perception of themselves and how they perform, and the success that they achieve. This study aims to address the importance coaches possess with their student-athletes by their behavior in practice or competition. After a thorough review of the seminal literature on SDT and the prominent studies on SDT applied to sports, the following research questions were designed to frame the study and scope of the eventual interview protocol:

RQ1

What are the perceptions that student-athletes hold about how a coach's behavior affects their athletic performance?

RQ2

What are the perceptions that student-athletes hold about how a coach's behavior affects their interpersonal relationships with teammates and coaches?

Summary

This study researched collegiate coach's behaviors and how this affects student-athletes performance, behavior, and relationships with coaching staff. This study utilized the Self-Determination Theory (SDT) to research student-athletes' motivation and personality behaviors.

This theory is widely used in sports and athletics, as it determines the motivational process of negative or positive experiences for student-athletes. This study emphasizes the importance of student-athlete relationships, communication, and perception of their coach's behavior.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

Self-Determination Theory (SDT) represents a broad framework for the study of human motivation and personality (Deci & Ryan, 2012). SDT is often used to frame motivational studies in order to define intrinsic and varied extrinsic sources of motivation, and to provide social scientists with a description of the respective roles of intrinsic and types of extrinsic motivation in cognitive and social development and in individual differences (Deci & Ryan, 2012). SDT focuses on how social and cultural factors facilitate or undermine one's sense of volition and initiative, in addition to their well-being and the quality of their performance (Bentzen et al., 2014).

Self-Determination Theory

SDT posits that there are two main types of motivation, intrinsic and extrinsic, and that both are powerful forces in shaping who we are and how we behave (Ryan & Deci, 2000). According to Deci and Ryan (1985), extrinsic motivation is a drive to behave in certain ways based on external sources and it results in external rewards. Such sources include grading systems, employee evaluations, awards and accolades, and the respect and admiration of others. Conversely, intrinsic motivation comes from within. There are internal drives that inspire us to behave in certain ways, including our core values, our interests, and our personal sense of morality (Deci & Ryan, 1985).

Both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation are highly influential determinants of our behavior, and both drive us to meet the three basic needs identified by the SDT model, autonomy, competence, and relatedness (Ryan & Deci, 2002). Autonomy is defined as the need people have to feel that they are the masters of their own destiny and that they have at least some control over their lives and the need to feel that they are in control of their own behavior (Deci &

Ryan, 2008). Competence is defined as the need one concerns themselves with their achievements, knowledge, and skills (Deci & Ryan, 2008). People have a need to build their competence and develop mastery over tasks that are important to them. Lastly, relatedness is the need one has to possess a sense of belonging and connectedness with others, as each of us needs other people to some degree (Deci & Ryan, 2008).

Conditions supporting an individual's experience of autonomy, competence, and relatedness are researched to identify the most effective forms of motivation and engagement for activities, including enhanced performance, persistence, and creativity (Bentzen et al., 2014). In addition, SDT proposes that the degree to which any of these three psychological needs is unsupported or thwarted within a social context will have a robust detrimental impact on wellness in that setting (Bentzen et al., 2014). The dynamics of psychological need have been studied within families, teams, athletic organizations, and cultures using specific propositions detailed within SDT (Jones et al., 2005). The SDT framework provides researchers with broad and behavior-specific implications for understanding practices and structures that enhance satisfaction and the full functioning that follows from it (Bentzen et al., 2014).

Self-Determination Theory & Athletics

SDT has been used in numerous studies exploring sports and athletics, as it offers a sound theoretical framework to better understand the motivational processes leading to serious positive and negative outcomes (Standage & Ryan, 2020). Bartholomew et al. raised awareness on the negative side of sport participation in their 2009 study, which proposed that coach behaviors employed to pressure or control athletes have the potential to thwart athletes' feelings of autonomy, competence, and relatedness, which, in turn, undermine athletes' self-determined motivation and contribute to the development of controlled motives. When athletes feel

pressured to behave in a certain way, a variety of negative consequences are expected to ensue which are to the detriment of the athletes' well-being (Bartholomew et al., 2009).

In 2014, Bentzen et al. conducted a study on four professional athletic coaches who had reported a wide range of burnout symptoms. Findings indicated that athletic coaches experience working in maladaptive environments, exemplified by experiencing very heavy workloads, a lack of leader support, and work-related conflicts (Bentzen et al., 2014). These experiences had a detrimental effect on the coaches' motivation. Psychological need thwarting and a shift towards a more controlled form of motivation explains why coaches became increasingly at risk for burning out, a process that has evolved over time (Bentzen et al., 2014). Findings from this study highlight the importance for sports organizations to better cater for the psychological needs of professional coaches to prevent burnout.

A 2006 study by Amorose and Anderson-Butcher further strengthened the applicability of SDT in sport and athletic participation. In their study, the authors used SDT to test whether perceived competence, autonomy, and relatedness mediated the relationship between perceived autonomy-supportive coaching and athletes' motivational orientation (Amorose & Anderson-Butcher, 2006). Their results indicated that the degree to which athletes perceived their coaches to be autonomy-supportive significantly predicted the athletes' perceived competence, autonomy, and sense of relatedness, which, in turn, each predicted their motivational orientation (Amorose & Anderson-Butcher, 2006).

Coach-Athlete Relational Dyad

Student athletes can cope with various coaches' behaviors and mechanisms based on their perception of their coach, as a key dyad within sport coaching is the coach-athlete dyad (Wachsmurth et al., 2016). Relationships can be created or changed from someone's perception

especially in a coach-athlete relationship. A relationship between the athlete and coach is crucial because this can affect the athlete's perception of themselves, their performance, and of course their coach (Wachsmurth et al., 2016). Each athlete will respond differently to a coach's behavior than their teammates do. According to Macquet (2013), it is important for the coach to build a strong relationship with each individual athlete to improve each other's understanding and logic with one another. The coach has to spend time with each athlete to know what coaching style fits him or her because this can cause issues down the road when the athlete doesn't respond well to his or her coaching style (Macquet, 2013). Each athlete prefers different coaching styles based on his or her personality, which is why it is important for coaches to change their behavioral techniques based on what their athletes' needs.

Communication is essential for everyday life, especially in a sport. The relationship between coach and athlete can affect the communication process among one another or among the team (Martin et al., 2009). Coaches play an important role in establishing effective communication channels across a team, as coaches are an essential part of team social and cultural arrangements (Jones et al., 2016). Athletes rely heavily on their coaches to communicate with them about their performance or understanding of the skill they perform. Feedback is critical for a coach to give to the athletes because this can alter the athlete's perception of their relationship with their coach as well as improving or changing their skill level (Martin et al., 2009). Communication can be difficult with many players who are performing at the same time, but maintaining the communication process to all athletes during practice and competition can better the relationship (Mata & Da Silva-Gomes, 2013).

According to Turman (2008), the relationship that exists between a coach and athlete has an impact on the athlete's performance or satisfaction during a competition. Likewise, in 2005,

Turman found that it doesn't matter if the players win or lose in a practice or game, as long as the coaches and players are on the same page with understanding what the athletes need to do to improve is the most essential function of team success. Not only does a coach have to improve daily on maintaining performance levels, but they must also work to build strong relationships with their athletes, as well.

In 2014, Outlaw and Toriello found that athletes who are more compatible with their teammates were more satisfied with the coach's behavior during competition. The coach's relationship with the athlete maintained a crucial position in athlete athletic satisfaction, but this study illustrated how strong teammates relationships should encourage a coach to adapt their behaviors during competition (Outlaw & Toriello, 2014). Adaptive coaching behavior can enhance relationships and further strengthen the coach-athlete dyad.

Research Questions

After a thorough review of the seminal literature on SDT and the prominent studies on SDT applied to sports, the following research questions were designed to frame the study and scope of the eventual interview protocol.

RQ1

What are the perceptions that student-athletes hold about how a coach's behavior affects their athletic performance?

RQ2

What are the perceptions that student-athletes hold about how a coach's behavior affects their interpersonal relationships with teammates and coaches?

Summary

This study sought to analyze whether coaches' behavior affects an athlete's perception of their performance or relationship with their coaching staff and teammates. More specifically, the study focuses on how a coach's behavior affects the athlete's relationship with one another, communication, perception of themselves and how they perform, and the success that they achieve. This study addresses the importance coaches possess with their student-athletes by their behavior in practice or competition.

Chapter 3: Research Method

This study set out to investigate collegiate athletic coaches' behavior and how their behavior affects student-athletes' perceptions of their performance and how their behavior affects student-athletes' relationships with their coaching staffs. The thematic analysis research design was chosen because of its ability to understand a set of experiences, thoughts, or behaviors across a data set (Braun & Clarke, 2012). The data set for this project consisted of interview transcripts from six individual semi-structured interviews with current collegiate student-athletes.

Research methods and design will be discussed in this chapter. Additionally, the population sample will be presented, as will materials, and study procedures in order to allow replication of this study. Finally, methods of data analysis including assumptions, limitations, delimitations, and ethical assurances are addressed.

Research Methodology and Design

A thematic analysis research design was utilized to reveal participant experiences that could reveal potential ways to target solutions to the research problem. Thematic analysis is a widely used, yet often misunderstood, method of qualitative data analysis (Kiger & Varpio, 2020). Thematic analysis is a method for analyzing qualitative data that entails searching across a data set to identify, analyze, and report repeated patterns (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

A distinguishing feature of thematic analyses is the flexibility to be used within a wide range of theoretical frameworks and to be applied to a wide range of study questions, designs, and sample sizes (Kiger & Varpio, 2020). Depending on the study, the data set might include interviews, focus groups, recorded observations, or field notes (Nowell et al. 2017). Thematic analysis can stand alone as an analytic method and be seen as foundational for other qualitative

research methods (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Because of this flexibility, Braun and Clarke (2006) refer to thematic analysis as a method, as opposed to a more tightly prescribed methodology. It has also been suggested that thematic analysis is a good first analytic method for novice qualitative researchers to master (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Thematic analysis is also a proven and appropriate method to use when seeking to understand a set of experiences, thoughts, or behaviors across a data set (Braun & Clarke, 2012), as I set out to do with this thesis.

Interviews can come in the form of structured interviews, unstructured interviews, or semi-structured interviews. Structured interviews are verbally administered questionnaires in which a predetermined list of questions is asked (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Saldana, 2021). Unstructured interviews do not reflect any preconceived theories or ideas and are performed with little organization (Creswell & Poth, 2018). Semi-structured interviews consist of key questions that help define the areas to be explored, but also allows the interviewer to diverge to pursue a response in more detail (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Saldana, 2021).

A thematic analysis analyzed through the lens of Self-Determination Theory (SDT) was utilized in this study. The three basic needs of SDT, competence, autonomy, and relatedness provided the initial themes and guiding framework employed throughout this study. Braun and Clark (2019) explained that thematic analyses are appropriate to use when seeking to understand lived experiences. If the objective of a qualitative study is to construct a comprehensive portrait of a phenomena, researchers can study several instances of the phenomena to identify commonalities (Ragin & Amoroso, 2019).

Population and Sample

The sample for this study consisted of six current student-athletes competing at an NCAA Division I institution. The sample included three male and three female student-athletes. Initial efforts to recruit started with distributing a recruitment email through the SUU Athletics Director of Academics. After the first two interviews, purposive sampling was used to recruit the participants. Purposive sampling refers to the non-probability sampling technique in which participants are selected because they have requisite characteristics needed for the study (Coombs, 2022). This sampling technique is widely used in qualitative research for the identification and selection of information-rich cases for the most effective use of limited resources (Saldana, 2021). Overall, 11 student-athletes agreed to participate in this study, although data saturation was reached after just five interviews. A sixth and final interview was conducted under the direction of my capstone chair, Dr. Hayden Coombs.

Materials

This qualitative thematic analysis utilized semi-structured interviews for data collection. Interview data offer uniform value directed toward addressing research questions (Braaten et al., 2020). An interview guide containing open-ended, semi-structured questions was created to generate relevant feedback from participants (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). As this study was designed to provide an understanding of how collegiate athletic coaches' behavior affects student-athletes' perceptions of their performance and student-athletes' relationships, the interview guide consisted of semi-structured interview questions guided by the study's research questions. The interview guide was created under the director of Dr. Hayden Coombs and the Southern Utah University (SUU) Institutional Review Board (IRB) after consulting consulting seminal literature on qualitative data collection (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Denzin & Lincoln, 2018; Saldana, 2021) and academic interview protocol (Katz-Buonincontro & Nezu, 2022;

Krueger & Casey, 2015; Straus, 2019). The interview protocol was reviewed by several experts in the field, including Dr. Hayden Coombs and Dr. Braden Bagley of the SUU Department of Communication who provided feedback on improving the final version of the interview guide and questions. Lastly, member checking efforts were made during the interview process at the conclusion of the interviews. The final interview guide that was followed through the duration of this study can be found in Appendix B.

Study Procedures

The initial steps of this project began with obtaining approval from the SUU IRB. Obtaining IRB approval for this project involved completing a CITI program course, drafting a non-disclosure and confidentiality agreement, letter of consent, recruitment email, and interview guide. After receiving approval from the SUU IRB, recruitment materials were emailed to the SUU Assistant Athletic Director for Academics, who then forwarded the recruitment materials to prospective subjects. Purposive sampling was used to recruit the participants. The interviews were scheduled for 45-minute sessions. Data from the interviews were collected through open-ended, semi-structured questioning. Handwritten field notes were also taken during the interviews. Collecting multiple types of information is a process called data triangulation (Yin, 2018). Data triangulation encourages researchers to collect information from multiple sources that corroborate the same findings (Yin, 2018). Transcripts from the interviews provided the textual artifacts that were coded and analyzed.

Data Analysis

In qualitative research, data analysis starts with the researcher creating units of analysis (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018). A unit of analysis is a meaningful segment that has the potential to

respond to part of a research question (Elliot, 2018). It can be as short as one word or as long as a paragraph (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018). The unit needs to satisfy two requirements: it must be relevant for the study and inspire the researcher to think beyond a specific word, phrase, or concept, and it must be the smallest piece of information that can be interpreted without any additional information (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018). As this study was designed to provide an understanding of how collegiate athletic coaches' behavior affects student-athletes' perceptions of their performance and student-athletes' relationships, units of analysis in this study were the three basic needs of Self-Determination Theory (SDT), competence, autonomy, and relatedness.

As previously stated, data were collected from student-athletes through individual semi-structured interviews. The data were analyzed through an open coding process. Data recordings from the focus groups and one-on-one individual interviews also provided feedback on verbal and nonverbal behaviors (Morgan, 2019). All interviews were recorded and transcribed verbatim in a Word document so coding could begin. Coding is the process of examining qualitative data by reducing them down to see what is generated before putting the data back together meaningfully (Elliott, 2018). Once the data was compiled, it was organized into clustered data arrangements.

Assumptions

Several assumptions were made throughout this study. The first and arguably most important assumption made is that those student-athletes who participated in the study were honest during the interview process and did not provide inaccurate or intentionally misleading representations of their experiences. Other assumptions include the belief that participants

produced enough data to support the study and that the participants will be an accurate representation of all student-athletes attending NCAA Division I institutions.

Limitations

Limitations are present in all investigative studies, which can refute research findings (Theofanidis & Fountouki, 2018). The first and most relevant limitation of this study is that it focuses exclusively on student-athletes competing at a single NCAA Division I institution, and does not address the experiences of student-athletes at other universities. Rather than evaluating any single coach, team, or institution; rather, this research seeks to identify how coaches' behaviors affect student-athlete performance and socialization. Because of the presence of study limitations, data triangulation must be utilized to authenticate participant response consistencies by maintaining a logical sequence of events that were followed throughout the study (Fusch et al., 2018). Lastly, there are various limitations associated with the research methods. According to Theofanidis & Fountouki (2018), the limitations of any study concern potential weaknesses that are usually out of the researcher's control and closely associated with the chosen research design, statistical model constraints, funding constraints, or other factors. An exploratory procedure using open-ended questions may cause a limitation in the answers given as personal and subjective (Straus, 2019). Another potential limitation is researcher bias (Goodrick, 2020).

Delimitations

Delimitations provide researchers with an opportunity to set specific parameters around a research study and to create a manageable timeline of events (Theofanidis & Fountouki, 2018). This study was delimited to student-athletes attending SUU, an NCAA Division I member

institution located in the intermountain west region of the United States. My pre-existing relationship with the SUU Department of Athletics and its student-athletes allowed data to be gathered promptly once IRB approval was obtained. The sample size was delimited as necessary once saturation was reached (Yin, 2018).

Ethical Assurances

Written approval from the SUU IRB was obtained before any research or data began. This procedure ensured that each participant's rights and privacy would remain protected throughout the entire course of the study. Additionally, there was no foreseeable risks or discomforts associated with this study. Names and any other personal information of participants in this study were kept strictly confidential. No student names were mentioned at any time in this thesis. No unnecessary participant data was included that would allow for identification of the participants. Despite these efforts to minimize risk, participants could still elect to skip any question they did not wish to answer, skip any activity, or stop participation at any time without fear of penalty. My role as the researcher was primarily to oversee this study as a facilitator and guide the participants to provide feedback relevant to the research questions.

Summary

This study set out to investigate collegiate athletic coaches' behavior and how their behavior affects student-athletes' perceptions of their performance and how their behavior affects student-athletes' relationships with their coaching staffs. The thematic analysis research design was chosen because of its ability to understand a set of experiences, thoughts, or behaviors across a data set. The data set for this project consisted of interview transcripts from six individual semi-structured interviews with current collegiate student-athletes who were

selected through purposive sampling. The data were analyzed through an open coding process. Once the data was compiled, it was organized into clustered data arrangements. This study was delimited to student-athletes attending Southern Utah University. My pre-existing relationship with the SUU Department of Athletics and its student-athletes allowed data to be gathered promptly once IRB approval was obtained. The sample size was delimited as necessary once saturation was reached.

Chapter 4: Findings

This study investigated collegiate athletic coaches' behaviors and how this behavior may affect student-athletes' perceptions of their performance or relationship with their coaching staffs and teammates. The tenets of this study assumes that a coach's behavior, communication, and relationships with their athletes affects the athletes' performance and their ability to be successful in their sport. A thematic analysis analyzed through the lens of Self-Determination Theory (SDT) was utilized in this study. After a thorough review of the seminal literature on SDT and the prominent studies on SDT applied to sports, research questions and an interview guide were designed to frame the scope of the study. Six current upperclass student-athletes served as the research subjects for this study. The data produced by the research participants are presented in this chapter.

Trustworthiness of the Data

The most credible studies in academic research provide assurance that data has been properly collected and interpreted so that any findings or conclusions accurately reflect what was studied (Yin, 2016). In qualitative research, the best studies are those which establish trustworthiness throughout the study (Adler, 2022). Trustworthiness was established throughout this study through multiple measures. First, I triangulated data by interviewing student-athletes across sex, sport, and nationality. I also attempted to generalize the findings of my study by defining terms, producing a comprehensive literature review, producing a well-written methodology, and clearly explaining how I produced and conducted the study. Lastly, I also employed numerous member-checking and expert review efforts to authenticate my data.

Results

This study researched student-athletes' perception of their coach's behavior. There were six student-athletes that participated in this research. The results of this study concluded that a coach's behavior can affect a student-athletes performance and their inter-squad relationships. This study was guided by the Self-Determination Theory (SDT). This theory determined the interview questions and the research conducted.

Each participant began playing in their sport between the ages of two to six years of age. The female participants started at a younger age than the male participants. Participants all received full athletic scholarships to Southern Utah University with tuition, books and living costs all paid. Results were found by participants choosing the university because of their coaches, only offer of scholarship, class size, and population of Cedar City.

All six participants concluded that they felt close to their coaching staff and they can trust their coach with discussing their athletic performance or personal information. Each of the participants described their relationship with their coach as open communication and able to discuss their athletic performance with their coach. Two of the participants reported that their coach was a "father figure" or "their second parent". Four participants found that discussing their athletic performance should be in a private setting such as an office for a more private conversation or not in front of other student-athletes. The other participants either had no issue discussing their athletic performance on or off the court, in front of others or it wasn't mentioned how or when they talk with their coach on their athletic performance. I also examined the relationship between the participant and their coach. Results showed that each participant has a good relationship with their coach. Trust was the most common word in discussing their

relationship with their coach. All participants resulted in trusting their coach with discussing their athletic performance.

Only one participant mentioned that they could only trust their coaching staff with specific personal information. She stated

“I feel like I can only share certain personal information. Depending on how personal it is I can share it, but I don’t want them knowing my whole business because the coach that I share my personal information with will share the information with the whole coaching staff. I don’t want each coach knowing my business and talking behind my back.”

Performing poorly can be stressful on both the student-athlete and coaching staff. During stressful moments or experiences a person may behave or react differently than they would if the situation was going smoothly (Bentzen et al., 2014). The male participants answered this question differently than the female participants. One of the male participants sees that their coach has the best interest at heart by knowing their coach's reaction to their poor performance is showing that they care.

“My coach’s reaction to my poor play is just him, knowing that I 'm not my best, and I could be a lot better. The high expectations that the coach has for me, that is the end of it, you can react to it poorly, or you can react to it, and turn it into motivation. And just prove your coach wrong, which is, which is really what it's all about.”

Another participant noted that he is fine with frustration and anger during his poor performance:

“Yells, gets frustrated, curses and is mad at the situation not us the athletes”. Coach gets mad at the play or practice, but moves on from it quickly, he doesn’t hold onto the past. He wants to be able to lead or coach the team and make us better players.”

The female student athletes have a different experience with their coaching staff when they are performing poorly. The participants answered:

“When we are practicing or in competition and we mess up or it isn’t going perfect, they tell us more things that we are doing wrong. They have high expectations for us and when we mess up it is a big deal and continue to talk about our mistakes.”

Performing at the best of your ability can be exciting and motivating to continue to succeed. Exceeding expectations for not only the student-athlete, but the coach can be beneficial for the whole athletic program. All participants in this research answered positive answers about their coach. One student-athlete expressed:

“He gets excited, happy, gives me a hug, and he makes a joke. This makes me perform better and it makes it easier to practice, play or compete.” You're doing a great job, just keep it up. And that goes a long way, he doesn't have to be constantly babysitting, you're doing good. You're doing so good. And then you have to have higher expectations for yourself.”

Emotional or psychological experiences can be triggering to someone's ability to perform at the best of their ability (Standage & Ryan, 2020). The females in this research had important and beneficial information for this research. Both participants expressed:

“If my coach yells at me I cry and break down. I no longer can perform well, I don’t yell well and do very badly.”

The male student-athletes acknowledged that yelling is different than frustration and answered:

“I respond well to him yelling at me, it motivates me, it shows me he cares, and is mad at my mistake.

Another participant focused on why their coach is yelling at them with the following quote:

“If you have a coach that is constantly yelling, and napping, you don't want to play for that person. There's a difference between reacting to poor performance and just yelling. I think yelling can be seen as highly negative. You never want to play for a coach that just yells, yells, and yells no matter what you do. So it definitely affects you. At the end of the day, you're an athlete, and if that's the coach, you play for them. You got yourself in that situation in the first place, you got to know who you're playing for, what their style is. And if you put yourself in that situation where you're playing for coaches, yells yells, yells, and you got to work through that. And like I said, turn it into motivation.”

A coach's behavior can change under stressful situations as practice and games are different pressure environments. Practice has a different expectation versus game day expectation. The male participants had similar answers to their coach's behavior on practice or game days:

“Coach is the same on game day and practice. He does whatever we need to adjust to making us better athletes, he is more locked in on game days because he is focused on the game.

There is a lot more pressure and he just thinks about what we can do to win.”

The female student-athletes notice that the coaches do act differently on game days versus practice, as seen in the following quote,

“The beginning of the week practices are very different from the end of the week practices. If it is going to be a stressful one then practices are a lot more stressful and more intense versus every day and a meet day. Meet days the coaches try to stay calm and do less crazy things, but that doesn't always happen. They are different on the day of competition versus practice day.”

Evaluation of the Findings

After conducting the research and concluding the findings from the student-athletes at Southern Utah University, the results were similar to previous research that has been conducted.

Studying research that other individuals conducted and seeing comparable results determines the importance of coach's behavior in collegiate sports. With many athletes in collegiate athletics and coaches interacting with their athletes on and off the court, it is essential to understand how their behavior can affect an athlete's performance, relationship, communication and interpersonal relationships with teammates.

The results conducted in this research were consistent with previous studies that have researched the effects of a coach's behavior and communication and how this affects the athlete's performance or perception of themselves. As stated, SDT has been used in multiple athletic studies to determine motivating factors for positive or negative outcomes. The subjects in this research determined the positive and negative behaviors that their coach portrays during practice and competition. While results were similar to other studies, the results from this study showed that athletes put a lot of pressure on themselves and teammates and it is crucial for coaches to be leaders, mentors and have an interpersonal relationship with their athletes.

SDT also discusses the social and cultural aspects of their coach's behavior and in previous studies, coaches' social and cultural aspects can positively influence a student-athletes performance (Deci & Ryan, 2012). The participants in this study also stated that the positive influence and behavior their coach portrays during competition improves their performance. Overall the findings in the research conducted comparable results to previous studies and this research should be conducted more as it can be beneficial to coaches and athletes in every sport.

Summary

This study researched the coach's positive and negative behavior and how it affects an athlete's performance. The results determined similar results to previous studies conducted and it concluded that student-athletes rely on their coach's behavior to determine their performance,

mental performance, communication and relationship. The student-athlete's all have different relationships, experiences with their coaching staff, but all emphasized the importance of how their coach's behavior affects their performance in a positive or negative way. The perception of themselves, teammates and coaches also has an impact on their performance and their ability to be successful. The results found that each student-athlete performs differently based on their coach's behavior, communication and relationships.

Chapter 5: Implications, Recommendations, and Conclusions

This study investigated collegiate athletics coaches' behavior and how it affects the athlete's relationship with one another, communication, perception of themselves and how they perform, and the success that they achieve. This study aims to address the importance coaches possess with their student-athletes by their behavior in practice or competition.

Thematic analysis analyzed through the lens of Self-Determination Theory (SDT) was utilized in this study. The three basic needs of SDT, competence, autonomy, and relatedness provided the initial themes and guiding framework employed throughout this study. Semi-structured interviews were conducted verbally through a list of questions in a questionnaire. Utilizing the SDT theory and semi-structured interviews, the results found that student-athletes do perform better when the coach's behavior is more positive and uplifting. Male participants were not as affected as female athletes when their coach's behavior is negative, but all participants felt that if their coach has positive behavior their performance is better. With only doing research on only student-athletes at Southern Utah University this limits the research to better understanding if a certain sporting coach's behavior affects the student-athletes performance. Researching more in depth of different gender sports can improve the research and education of more individuals involved in collegiate sports.

Included in this study are the results of interviews of the student-athletes that were conducted and the perception the student-athletes have of their coach's behavior. Used in this research were semi-structured interviews using open-ended questions about the student-athletes coach's behavior, relationship, and communication. Student-athletes provided information on

how their coach's behaviors differed from practice and competition settings and how this affected their overall performance and perception.

Implications

As illustrated in this study, student-athletes demonstrated the importance of the coach's behavior on their athletic performance, communication, and relationships with their coaches and teammates. This research reinforces the existing literature about the Coach-Athlete Relational Dyad. It suggests future research can educate female student-athletes coaches to understand that female athletes interpret behavior and criticism differently than males.

Research Question 1

In researching previous studies about coaches' perceptions and behaviors on student-athletes' performance, all research examined the student-athlete perceptions. The results of this study indicate that future research should study in more depth the gender difference perception of coaches' behavior. The female participants in this study determined that their athletic performance was worse and responded more emotionally to criticism when their coach was portraying negative behavior. They also didn't feel as comfortable disclosing personal information to their coaches, but the males asked their coaches for advice in their personal lives. The male participants were also affected by their coaches' behaviors, but were able to continue to perform or not demonstrate emotion from the behavior quicker. This study suggests that female student-athletes perform better under positive and uplifting coaching methods, but the male student-athletes were not significantly affected by positive or negative reinforcement.

Research Question 2

This study suggests that communication and relationships with student-athletes can affect their athletic performance. As found in previous studies, communication and building

relationships with student-athletes can improve their overall performance and mental health (Amorose & Anderson-Butcher, 2006). This study suggests that relationships and communication are vital to the success of athletes and a program. This applies not only to collegiate sports, but to everyone's life. This research is essential for mentors or leaders in an organization, personal life, or sports, as anyone's behavior can affect their overall performance and perception of themselves.

Recommendations for Practice

As presented in this research, SDT is used to understand motivation factors and student-athletes' personalities. As researched previously, professional athletic coaches demonstrated burnout symptoms among their student-athletes (Bentzen, 2014). Coaches demonstrating positive behaviors in practice or during game days could avoid burnout symptoms. Coaches providing constructive feedback, encouragement, and praise can also enhance their student-athletes' performance to be better. Coaches should avoid overly negative feedback, which can affect the athletes' mental or emotional health and contribute to an unrealistic negative perception of their performance. The results from this study emphasize the importance for collegiate sports to understand and prioritize both the psychological and physiological needs of their student-athletes to avoid or prevent burnout.

Relationships between student-athletes and coaches can be crucial for performance and self-perception (Wachsmurth et al., 2016). Because of their complex relationship, student-athletes respond differently to their coaches' behavior than other athletes. Recruiting and building a relationship with the student-athlete is vital to the success of the program and a student-athlete's performance. Communication and building interpersonal relationships can improve a student-athlete's mental health by having clear expectations of the coach's behavior and performance (Martin et al., 2009). Interpersonal communication and relationships are also crucial

because student-athletes spend many hours in the program. Close relationships with the coaching staff and teammates can also improve their performance. The student-athletes not only want to be successful with their performance, but also their relationship with all involved in the program. Using SDT in collegiate coaching can help build effective communication and stronger relationships, which will improve student-athlete performance and team relationships.

Recommendations for Future Research

With collegiate athletics growing into a billion-dollar industry and NCAA regulations continuing to change, it is crucial to continue studying these students' emotional and educational landscapes. Identifying methods and theories for coaches to improve their coaching methods, such as communication, relationship building, and providing adequate emotional support, can benefit their program in the future. Coaches should be educating themselves on how each student-athlete needs to be coached. Student-athletes all have different methods on how they prefer to be coached for their sports, so coaches need to learn the best coaching method for their student-athletes. This study, along with previous studies, demonstrates the need to educate coaches on coaching methods and bring awareness of how impactful their behavior is on their student-athlete's athletic performance and self-perception.

With coaches improving their coaching styles and methods, this study can benefit future researchers by examining the limitations. To improve this research, given the limitation of only using student-athletes from a single institution, student-athletes need to understand that this research can benefit them as well. Future research interviewing current and former student-athletes would allow more diverse results. Researching participants from all sports in the university would be helpful in getting more information on the situation. Conversely, more

attention could be given to a single coach if one was to study a single team, which would produce hyper-focused results.

While this research took a student-athlete perspective, studying the coach's behavior on their self-perception, further research could explore the coach's perception of their athlete's practice and performance behaviors. Finding theories and methods in how the coach views their student-athletes could improve team communication. This research also has the potential to enhance student-athlete leadership. Approaching both perspectives as important and distinct is necessary for future research.

Conclusions

This study emphasizes the importance of a coach's behavior, as it affects their student-athletes' communication, self-perception, and relationships. This research further emphasizes the influence that coaches have on their student-athletes through their behavior in practice or competition. Throughout their collegiate journeys, student-athletes will spend many hours with their coaching staff. Building strong relationships, establishing effective communication channels, and setting realistic expectations is important for all the parties involved. As participants in this study said, their coaches are "father figures" or "my second set of parents."

The coach's behavior towards their student-athletes can affect their self-perception and the perceptions of their athletic performance. The participants of this study reported that when their coach's behavior and attitude were positive during practice or competition, their performance improved, they felt no added pressure on themselves, and their communication was better. The results concluded from this research reinforced previous studies on coaching behavior. With this research, it is important to educate not just collegiate athletes but upcoming athletes and coaches. This study also effectively informs coaches on how impactful their

behavior is toward their student-athletes. The findings of this research can also improve collegiate programs across the country, as fewer student-athletes will experience physical and emotional burnout, experience fewer mental health issues related to their athletic performance, and establish healthier communication routines with their coaches. In conclusion, coaches should strive to create a positive, supportive environment for their student-athletes to better their overall performance and self-perception.

Reference

- Amorose, A. J., & Anderson-Butcher, D. (2007). Autonomy-supportive coaching and self-determined motivation in high school and college athletes: A test of self-determination theory. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise, 8*(5), 654–670.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2006.11.003>
- Bartholomew, K. J., Ntoumanis, N., & Thogersen-Ntoumani, C. (2009). A review of controlling motivational strategies from a self-determination theory perspective: Implications for sports coaches. *International Review of Sport and Exercise Psychology, 2*(2), 215–233.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17509840903235330>
- Bentzen, M., Lemyre, P.-N., & Kenttä, G. (2014). The process of burnout among professional sport coaches through the lens of self-determination theory: A qualitative approach. *Sports Coaching Review, 3*(2), 101–116. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21640629.2015.1035050>
- Bloomberg, L. D., & Volpe, M. (2022). *Completing your qualitative dissertation: A road map from beginning to end* (5th ed.). SAGE. <https://us.sagepub.com/en-us/nam/completing-your-qualitative-dissertation/book279950>
- Booton, C. (2018). Using rich pictures to verify, contradict, or enhance verbal data. *The Qualitative Report, 23*(11), 2835-2849. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2018.3279>
- Braun V, Clarke V. 2006. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qual Res Psychol. 3*(2), 77–101.
- Braun V, Clarke V. 2012. Thematic analysis. *APA handbook of research methods in psychology, 2*. American Psychological Association.

- Coombs, H. (2022). The complex identities of international student-athletes competing in the NCAA: an exploratory qualitative case study [Doctoral dissertation, Northcentral University]. ProQuest.
- Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2018). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (4th ed.). Sage.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). *Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behavior*. Plenum.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2012). Self-determination theory. *Handbook of Theories of Social Psychology: Volume 1*, 416–437. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781446249215.n21>
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2008). Self-determination theory: A macrotheory of human motivation, development, and health. *Canadian psychology/Psychologie canadienne*, 49(3), 182
- Hollembeak, J., & Amorose, A. J. (2007, February 23). *Perceived coaching behaviors and college athletes' intrinsic motivation: A test of self-determination theory*. Taylor & Francis. Retrieved January 21, 2023, from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/10413200590907540?scroll=top&needAccess=true&role=tab>
- Horn, T. S. (2008). Coaching effectiveness in the sport domain. In T. S. Horn (Ed.), *Advances in sport psychology* (pp. 239–267, 455–459). Human Kinetics.
- Jones, R. L., Armour, K. M., & Potrac, P. (2005). *Sports coaching cultures: From practice to theory*. Routledge.

- Jones, R. L., Edwards, C., & Viotto Filho, I. A. (2014). Activity theory, complexity and sports coaching: An epistemology for a discipline. *Sport, Education and Society*, 21(2), 200–216. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13573322.2014.895713>
- Kiger, M. E., & Varpio, L. (2020). Thematic analysis of qualitative data: A mee Guide no. 131. *Medical Teacher*, 42(8), 846–854. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0142159x.2020.1755030>
- Knoester, C., & Ridpath, B. D. (2021). Should college athletes be allowed to be paid? A public opinion analysis. *Sociology of Sport Journal*, 38(4), 399–411. <https://doi.org/10.1123/ssj.2020-0015>
- Macquet, A. (2013). Getting Them on the Same Page: A Method to Study the Consistency of Coaches' and Athletes' Situation Understanding During Training Sessions and Competitions. *Sport Psychologist*, 27(3), 292-295.
- Martin, M. M., Rocca, K. A., Cayanus, J. L., & Weber, K. (2009). Relationship between Coaches' use of Behavior Alteration Techniques and Verbal Aggression on Athletes' Motivation and Affect. *Journal Of Sport Behavior*, 32(2), 227-241.
- Mata, R. T., & Da Silva-Gomes, A. R. (2013). Winning or Not Winning: The influence on Coach- Athlete Relationships and Goal Achievement. *Journal Of Human Sport & Exercise*, 8(4), 986-995.
- Miles, D. A. (2019). Research Methods and Strategies: Achieving Alignment: How to Develop Research Alignment In A Dissertation Study. *Research Methods and Strategies: Achieving Alignment*. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333772680_UPDATED_ARTICLE_Research_Methods_and_Strategies_Achieving_Alignment_How_to_Develop_Research_Alignment_In_A_Dissertation_Study.

- National Collegiate Athletic Association. (n.d.). *Scholarships*. NCAA.org. Retrieved June 20, 2022, from <https://www.ncaa.org/sports/2014/10/6/scholarships.aspx>
- Nyumba, T. O., Wilson, K., Derrick, C. J., & Mukherjee, N. (2018). The use of focus group discussion methodology: Insights from two decades of application in conservation. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 9(1), 20–32. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210x.12860>
- Outlaw, K. R., & Toriello, P. J. (2014). The Impact of Coaches' Behavior on African American Female Athletes' Playing Satisfaction: A cursory Review of the Literature. *Journal Of Human Behavior In The Social Environment*, 24(5), 612-620.
doi:10.1080/10911359.2014.914831
- Ragin, C. C., & Amoroso, L. M. (2019). *Constructing Social Research: The unity and diversity of Method*. SAGE.
- Ryan, R. M. (2013). The 2013 Self-Determination Theory Conference. In *Keynote Address*. Rochester, NY; Center for Self-Determination Theory. Retrieved January 21, 2023, from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3sRBBNkSXpY>.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *American Psychologist*, 55, 68-78
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2002). Overview of self-determination theory: An organismic dialectical perspective. *Handbook of self-determination research*, 2, 3-33.
- Saldana, J. (2021). *The coding manual for qualitative researchers*. Sage.
- Scholarship Stats. (2021). *US Colleges awarded over \$ 4 billion in Athletic Scholarships during 2019-20*. ScholarshipStats.com. Retrieved January 21, 2023, from <https://scholarshipstats.com/average-per-athlete/>

Turman, P. D. (2008). Coaches' Immediacy Behaviors as Predictors of Athletes' Perceptions of Satisfaction and Team Cohesion. *Western Journal Of Communication*, 72(2), 162-179.

doi:10.1080/10570310802038424

Turman, P. D. (2005). Coaches' Use of Anticipatory and Counterfactual Regret Messages During Competition. *Journal Of Applied Communication Research*, 33(2), 116-138.

doi:10.1080/00909880500045072

Wachsmuth, S., Jowett, S., & Harwood, C. G. (2016). Conflict among athletes and their coaches: What is the theory and research so far? *International Review of Sport and Exercise*

Psychology, 10(1), 84–107. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1750984x.2016.1184698>

Appendix A

Consent Letter

Introduction

My name is Ciera Martin. I am a candidate for the Master's of Professional Communication degree here at SUU. I am conducting a research study on coach behavior and student-athlete self-perception.

I am seeking your consent to participate in this study.

Please read this document to learn more about this study and determine if you would like to participate. Your participation is completely voluntary, and I will address your questions or concerns at any point before or during the study.

The Institutional Review Board (IRB) of SUU has reviewed this study for the protection of the rights of human subjects in research studies, in accordance with federal and state regulations. If you have any concerns about this study, you may email the SUU IRB at irb@suu.edu.

Eligibility

You may participate in this research if you meet all of the following criteria:

1. Are of age 18 or older.
2. Attend college at Southern Utah University.
3. Participate in an NCAA Division I sport and are therefore considered a "student-athlete."

I hope to include up to 6 people in this research.

Activities

If you decide to participate in this study, you will be asked to do the following activities:

1. Complete an online survey for 5-10 minutes.
2. Participate in a 1:1 online interview over Zoom for 45-60 minutes.
3. Review your interview transcript via email for 15-20 minutes.

During these activities, you will be asked questions about:

- Your age, gender, race, and nationality.
- The sport you play at the NCAA Division I level.
- Your adjustment transitioning from high school to collegiate athletics.
- Your experience being coached at the NCAA Division I level.

- Your experience participating in NCAA Division I athletics.
- Your experience socializing with teammates.

All interviews will be conducted via Zoom. The interviews will be audio recorded only.

This study seeks to analyze whether coaches' behavior affects an athlete's perception of their performance or relationship with their coaching staff. More specifically, the study focuses on how a coach's behavior affects the athlete's relationship with one another, communication, perception of themselves and how they perform, and the success that they achieve. This study aims to address the importance coaches possess with their student-athletes by their behavior in practice or competition.

All activities and questions are optional: you may skip any part of this study that you do not wish to complete and may stop at any time.

If you need to complete the activities above in a different way than I have described, please let me know, and I will attempt to make other arrangements.

Risks

There potentially could be unforeseeable risks of emotional trauma, psychological experience such as stress or anxiety that the student-athlete could feel during the interview questions. If the student-athlete is experiencing any of the risks, they don't have to continue or answer the question and I will provide them with Southern Utah Caps information. I will mandate any risks by asking graduating senior student-athletes. With this research, I am seeking to better understand how a student-athlete's self-perception is affected by their coaches. I am not evaluating any single coach, team, or institution; rather, I am seeking to identify methods of which coaching staffs can offer better support measures for their student-athletes, thus leading to better athletic and social experiences in college. I will take reasonable measures to protect the security of all your personal information, and your participation in this study will never be revealed to any coach, administrator, or student-athlete. Topics addressed during the interview will include coaching, coach behavior, and criticism. If any topic makes you uncomfortable or you do not wish to answer, you may elect to skip any question, activity, or stop participation at any time.

Risks included talking about negative experiences can be triggering such as an emotional experience. Menated the risk we are only talking with graduating senior student athletes where they are

Benefits

If you participate, there are no direct benefits to you. This research may increase the body of knowledge in the subject area of this study.

Privacy and Data Protection

I will take reasonable measures to protect the security of all your personal information, but I cannot guarantee confidentiality of your research data. In addition to me, the following people and offices will have access to your data:

- My capstone chair, Dr. Hayden Coombs.
- The SUU Institutional Review Board

This data could be used for future research studies or distributed to other investigators for future research studies without additional informed consent from you or your legally authorized representative.

I will securely store your data, then I will delete electronic data after I have defended my capstone in April 2023.

How the Results Will Be Used

I will publish the results in my thesis. I may also share the results in a presentation or publication. Participants will not be identified in the results.

Recording

I would like to record your responses with Zoom during the interview process.

Contact Information

If you have questions, you can contact me at: cieramartin@suu.edu or 702-491-7880.

My capstone chair's name is Dr. Hayden Coombs. He works at Southern Utah University and is supervising me on the research. You can contact him at: haydencoombs@suu.edu.

If you have questions about your rights in the research or if a problem or injury has occurred during your participation, please contact the SUU Institutional Review Board at irb@suu.edu.

Voluntary Participation

If you decide not to participate, or if you stop participation after you start, there will be no penalty to you: you will not lose any benefit to which you are otherwise entitled. You may ask questions at any time before or after the interview by emailing me at cieramartin@suu.edu. You can also ask questions at any time during the interview.

Appendix B

Interview Guide

Introduce myself and ensure the participant(s) is/are in a comfortable and confidential place. Ask if the participant needs more time to ensure the video conference is confidential. Review the consent form, which the participants signed and sent back to me.

Read the following statement: “The Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Southern Utah University has reviewed this study for the protection of the rights of human subjects in research studies, in accordance with federal and state regulations. If you have any concerns about this study, you may email the SUU IRB at irb@suu.edu.”

Ask the participants if they have any questions.

Interview Questions

1. What sport do you play at Southern Utah University?
2. What is your age and what age did you begin playing your sport?
3. Why did you pick Southern Utah University to continue your athletic career?
4. How would you describe your relationship with your coaching staff?
5. Do you feel that you can discuss with your coach about your athletic performance? Why or why not? Please explain your answer.
6. How have your coaches shown that they have your best interest at heart? Please explain your answer.
7. How have you felt that your coaches didn't act in your best interest? Please explain your answer.
8. Do you trust your coach with personal information? Why or why not?
9. How does your coach react to your athletic performance when you perform poorly? Why or why not?
10. How does this reaction effect you personally, athletically, or any other way? Please explain your answer.
11. How does your coach react to your athletic performance when you perform well or exceed expectations? Please explain your answer.
12. How does this reaction effect you personally, athletically, or any other way? Please explain your answer.
13. How do you perform when your coaches yell at you?
14. How do you perform with your coach talking in a calm voice?
15. How is your coach's behavior during practice? Game and/or game day?
16. What do you think your coaches and teammates think about you?
17. What do you look for in a great coach?
18. Is there a coach or athlete that you look up to as a role model? Why?
19. What is the best advice you've gained from your coaches?

Ask the participant if they have anything else to add. Thank the participant for their involvement and remind them that they will have the opportunity to review the final transcripts before data analysis.

Appendix C

IRB Approval Letter

*Institutional Review Board
351 W University Blvd., ED 325
Cedar City, UT, 84720
irb@suu.edu*

To: Ciera Martin (PI) and Hayden Coombs (Faculty Supervisor)
From: William J. Davis (Chair, SUU Institutional Review Board)
Subject: IRB Approval Protocol #24-042023a
Date: April 24, 2023

Please be informed that as of the date of this letter, the Institutional Review Board for Research on Human Participants at Southern Utah University has given full approval to your study, entitled “**Coach Behavior and Student-Athlete Self-Perception,**” under **Expedited Review Category 7** (study of group characteristics).

This approval **does not expire**. Studies approved under Expedited review categories do not require an expiration date.

The IRB Committee must be contacted if any unexpected risks to participants become evident, or if the study deviates from the approved protocol in any other way. Should you have questions, or if you want to make changes to your approved protocol, please do not hesitate to contact the IRB (irb@suu.edu). Please reference your protocol number when you contact the IRB.

Best wishes for your research work.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "William J. Davis".

William J. Davis, Ed.D.

irb@suu.edu

Appendix D

SUU Institutional Repository Permission Form

Gerald R. Sherratt Library
351 W. University Blvd.
Cedar City, UT 84720
435-865-8241
thesis@suu.edu

Permission to Include Thesis or Selected Project
in SUU Institutional Repository

DIRECTIONS FOR STUDENT

Complete this form and obtain the necessary signatures.

Submit the completed form with a digital copy of the thesis to thesis@suu.edu.

Note that theses must include title page and signature page.

Name: (as it appears on the thesis or project)			SUU ID <u>T 01054997</u>
<u>Ciera J. Martin</u>			<u>Communications</u>
First	Middle or Initial	Last or Surname	Department
<u>370 W. 1425 N #36 Cedar City, UT 84721</u>			<u>702-491-7880</u>
Permanent Street Address			Daytime telephone number
Departmental Approval			
The graduate committee chair and the department chair have read the work in its final form and have found that it meets university and departmental content and format requirements. Its format, citations, and bibliographic style are consistent and acceptable; its illustrative materials including figures, tables and charts are in place; the final manuscript is acceptable to the graduate committee and is ready for submission to the university library.			
Signature of Graduate Committee Chair		Date	Signature Department Chair
			<u>4/25/23</u>
			Date
Student Agreement			
My graduate committee and I agree that the document described in this application should be placed in the SUU Institutional Repository. I will provide key words that can be used to access my paper, an abstract of my thesis and electronic copy of the work in pdf format to the Sherratt Library and agree to release the entire work immediately for worldwide access.			
I hereby certify that, if appropriate, I have obtained and attached hereto a written permission statement from the owner(s) of each third-party copyrighted matter to be included in my thesis or selected project, and will allow inclusion in the Institutional Repository. I certify that the version I am submitting is the same as that approved by my graduate committee.			
I hereby grant to Southern Utah University and its agents the non-exclusive license to archive and make accessible my thesis or selected project in whole or in part in all forms of media, now or hereafter known. I retain all other ownership rights to the copyright of the theses or selected project. I also retain the right to use in future works (such as articles or books) all or part of this thesis or selected project.			
		<u>Ciera Martin</u>	<u>4/24/23</u>
Student Signature		Name of student (printed)	Date